

Impact Study

Crop

Improvement

Crop Improvement

Context

The accelerating pace of climate change presents one of the greatest challenges to global food systems. Rising temperatures, increasingly sporadic weather patterns, and the spread of crop diseases [threaten agricultural productivity](#) and the livelihoods of millions of [smallholder farmers](#). At the same time, growing populations are placing added pressure on food production systems to deliver more, with fewer resources and under increasingly unstable conditions.

This case study explores how biodata resources are enabling innovation in crop science and agricultural research and opening up opportunities to accelerate the development of climate-smart crops.

Joining forces to tackle spreading wheat disease

Wheat blast is a fungus that can [devastate valuable crops](#). It was first identified in [Brazil](#) in 1985, before spreading across South America for the following three decades. In 2016, it emerged in [Bangladesh](#) and affected over 15,000 hectares of fields. [Zambia](#) also experienced a wheat blast pandemic in 2019, marking the first occurrence of the disease in Africa.

To respond to these emergencies, [OpenWheatBlast](#) was launched to ensure the prompt and open release of relevant data and analyses; the project benefits from the participation of more than [50 international collaborators](#) from 11 different countries. By pooling genomic evidence from multiple outbreaks, OpenWheatBlast enables researchers to trace a pathogen's origins, monitor its evolution and uncover how wheat blast spreads across regions. These efforts also support breeding disease-resistant wheat varieties and enable early detection and response to future outbreaks, helping to safeguard global wheat production.

For their contribution to [mitigating the spreading wheat blast pandemic](#), one of the OpenWheatBlast leads was awarded the 2023 Innovation and Impact Award for Outstanding Impact in Policy and Practice from the University of East Anglia. Sophien Kamoun, co-lead of OpenWheatBlast, reflects on the project's significance and its legacy:

"OpenWheatBlast showed how open biodata resources can transform our ability to respond to plant disease threats by enabling global collaboration in real time. Building on this momentum, we launched [GetGenome](#) to extend the principle of equitable, open genomics to all researchers, especially those in under-resourced regions. Sustaining such resources is vital — not only for crop improvement, but for ensuring that the benefits of genomics are shared widely and fairly."

Genomic editing for public health

[CRISPR/Cas9](#) is a gene-editing technology that allows scientists to precisely edit DNA sequences. After a [Nobel Prize](#) was awarded for developing the technology in 2020, CRISPR/Cas9 has received significant media attention for its potential applications in human health. However, its role in plant science has been less widely recognised.

The genome of the [Sicilian Rouge High GABA tomato](#) was edited using CRISPR to have 7-15 times higher gamma-aminobutyric acid content than ordinary tomatoes. GABA is a natural compound known to help reduce stress, improve sleep and lower blood pressure in humans, and getting more of it from food could support mental and physical well-being. These tomatoes were created by tweaking the plant's own genes to boost GABA production. After testing with a community of 4,000 home growers across Japan, these tomatoes are [now sold by Sanatech Seed Co](#) (a venture company launched from the University of Tsukuba) in grocery stores, as well as being used in select restaurants in Tokyo.

Sequence data from NCBI's [GenBank](#), a part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration ([INSDC](#)), was essential in deciding where and how to use CRISPR. It enabled cross-species comparison of GAD sequences, the identification of functional domains, the design of CRISPR targets to remove inhibitory regions and the prediction of biochemical outcomes. The [detailed methodology](#) shared by the authors also sheds light on a broader range of biodata and bioinformatics resources and tools that enabled this discovery, including [ClustalW](#), [Jalview](#) (which incorporates data from Pfam, Rfam, PDBe, UniProt, ENA, Ensembl and more) and the [Tomato eFP Browser](#).

Importantly, Sicilian Rouge High GABA tomatoes were the world's first CRISPR tomato launched to a Japanese market. Japan was also the first country in the world to launch genome-edited unprocessed crops, which is expected to have a [significant impact](#) on the development of rules for the handling of genetically engineered crops worldwide.

Developing resilient crops to protect against climate change

The [International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center \(CIMMYT\)](#), part of [CGIAR](#) (a global research partnership for a food-secure future), has launched a US\$25.7 million project to tap into the genetic diversity conserved in [CGIAR's global network of genebanks](#).

CGIAR genebanks are a global network of repositories that conserve, manage and distribute the world's most diverse, publicly available collections of crop genetic resources, including seeds, tissue cultures, tubers, and cryopreserved samples from over 3,000 species. These collections account for about [94% of germplasm](#) and are recognised as “international public goods” by, and managed under, the auspices of the [International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture](#).

At the 15th meeting of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (COP15) [scientists from CIMMYT and CGIAR presented](#) ways in which digital sequence information (digitised biological data, like DNA sequences from the natural world) is changing the application of genetic resources in agricultural research and development and implications for new [benefit-sharing norms](#).

This high-profile engagement with global policymakers was informed by projects across the Allele Mining Initiative and through leveraging the CGIAR Genebanks, including [Mining Useful Alleles](#) and [Fast Tracking Climate Solutions](#), alongside [earlier work funded by the Mexican Government](#).

Conclusions

These case studies demonstrate how strategic investment in biodata infrastructure and open science collaboration can deliver tangible solutions to agriculture's most pressing challenges. The success of OpenWheatBlast in containing a rapidly spreading pandemic, the commercial deployment of GABA-enhanced tomatoes in Japan and CGIAR's systematic approach to mining genetic diversity all share common elements: comprehensive data sharing, international cooperation and the integration of cutting-edge genomic tools with practical agricultural applications.

As climate pressures intensify, scaling these approaches will require not just continued scientific innovation, but deliberate investment that makes such breakthroughs possible. The question is not whether biodata can transform agriculture, but how quickly and equitably these transformations can reach the communities that need them most.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
CGIAR Genbank Platform	The CGIAR Genbank Platform, led by the Crop Trust, supports 11 genbanks that conserve and distribute crop and tree germplasm. The Platform ensures collections meet international standards for availability, safety duplication, documentation, and policy compliance.
CLUSTALW	CLUSTALW is a bioinformatics tool for multiple sequence alignment of DNA, RNA or protein sequences. CLUSTALW can align any number of homologous nucleotide or protein sequences to identify regions of similarity that may indicate functional, structural, or evolutionary relationships.
GenBank	GenBank is the NIH genetic sequence database, providing an annotated collection of all publicly available DNA sequences. It is part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration alongside the DNA DataBank of Japan (DDBJ) and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), with daily data exchange between these organisations.
Jalview	Jalview is a cross-platform bioinformatics tool which began development in 1995 and supports users with multiple sequence alignments. Jalview provides capability for editing, visualisation and analysis, particularly useful for in-depth sequence analysis required when exploring new RNA or protein sequences families.

Resources	About
Open Wheat Blast	<p>OpenWheatBlast is an open data platform providing genetic and other datasets related to wheat blast, a fungal disease that threatens wheat production. The platform was established to enable rapid response to disease outbreaks, generating genetic information directly from diseased plant samples. All data and analyses are released publicly without restrictions, with datasets available through the website and the OpenWheatBlast Zenodo Community.</p>
Tomato eFP Browser	<p>Tomato eFP Browser is an interactive tool that draws on gene expression databases to visualise gene expression in tomato plants. It supports understanding of which plant tissues express specific genes, with the capability to visualise up to 40 genes simultaneously. Visualisations cover various aspects of the plant including cellular, whole plant, leaf, and fruit tissues.</p>
UniProt	<p>UniProt is the world's leading high-quality, comprehensive, and freely accessible resource of protein sequences and functional annotation, featuring the expert-curated core. UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot. UniProt is mainly supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI, EMBL, and the US National Institutes of Health (NIH).</p>

Global Biodata Coalition

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